

Electricity Meter Reading Using Machine Learning

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Abstract — This article introduces an image-based meter reading using machine learning. In this process, mainly obtain an efficient and accurate reading of meter. This system is used to insert an image on the basis of camera and extract the digits accurately. The major stages are preprocessing, segmentation of digits in horizontal and vertical scanning. Extract the digits and display on text.

The proposed system is implemented in machine learning using openCV and OCR.

Keywords—image processing, digit segmentation, digit recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

In our daily life, electricity is quite important. Every day, people use more electricity. We rely on it so much and for so many things that we can't picture our lives without it. Electric meter used to track how much electricity is consumed. The goal of this project is to make the electricity meter reading process easier for employees of electricity companies in Kerala, as the current method of manual electricity meter reading is ineffective with rising electricity consumption.

To acquire efficient and reliable readings of digital electricity meter, we introduce a system based on image processing. This work adds value by extracting information. The method for recognizing image processing: Pre-processing includes clipping the numeric reading area, sub-division of individual digits utilizing horizontal and vertical scanning of the clipped numeric region, and recognition of the reading via comparing each segmented digit with the digit patterns.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Lamiaa A. Elrefaei et al [1] propose. To implement The Android Studio software, which uses the openCV library, was tested on 21 photographs of electric meter taken with a camera phone in Saudi Arabia, and the findings show that the recognition rate is 96.49 percent and 85.71 percent for the power meter readings. The proposed method would be used to develop a mobile application that power company technicians can use to make the reading process easier.

Nuntid Sripanuskul et al [2] develop. Although smart meter are not yet widely used in many areas, periodic reading of traditional meter is beneficial in terms of expense and reliability. Despite its high potential for automatic meter reading in an uncontrolled environment, the convolutional neural network (CNN) faces a number of problems. One issue is the difficulty in collecting a large enough training sample, as some meter digits can take much longer to reset. Another difficult problem is identifying the intermediate condition between two consecutive numbers. We present a new data augmentation technique that can simply create images of data, including going through similar, to overcome these difficulties.

Jameer Kotwal, et al [3] developed an Android App for Meter Reading which tells about We're working on an Android app as well as a website application. Only meter readers can use the Android app. The reading on the meter. This option is more advantageous for Readers of meter. The meter reader has a bag with him at the start of the day. To get the meter, you'll need an Android phone with an Android app. The basic technique is to take a picture of the meter and then read it within a day. With the help of the Android app, the data was sent to the server. In the server room on one hand, the process of obtaining meter reading text from the picture will be created. Furthermore, the server performs the calculations. Then subsequent bills are emailed to the appropriate customers.

Lei Feng, Chuang et al [4] developed an Android APP Development of Remote Wireless Automatic Meter Reading System based on 3G. This article demonstrates the construction of a remote wireless automatic meter reading and control system. This includes setting up a TCP server and accompanying service application, designing an Oracle database, and creating an APP for a mobile terminal. Managers do not need to keep an eye on any computer screen information enquiry, nor do they need to enter the harsh environment of the scene; instead, they simply open the mobile APP, and they can instantly understand the relevant information in a helpful, efficient, and systematic manner.

Nitesh Rawat et al [5], A review paper on automatic energy meter reading system. There will be normally wired AMR devices such as Power Line Communications, phone Line Networks, and wireless AMR systems like as E-metering systems used in these regional units. The style of these devices for long-distance data transfer is based on GPRS but this approach can't be imposed merely because constant use of GPRS is still a vision for those.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find a Machine Learning model to check the meter reading. This model is used to check the meter reading accurately and using OPENCV and OCR and finding the accuracy of an image.

Fig. 1: Image processing using electricity meter:

1. Upload image
2. Pre-processing
3. Machine Learning
4. Build Model
5. Result

A. Upload image: User have to upload an images by camera using opencv and esay OCR.

B. Pre-processing: This is the step that is done in every machine learning method. This process includes data Cleaning, transformation of data, and data reduction are all steps in the data transformation and reduction process. All of this is done in order to improve the effectiveness of the data. We can use the data to improve the accuracy of our model. In order to ensure that the classification is accurate. Resize the image, convert it to grayscale, blur it, and construct an edge map as part of the pre-processing procedure.

1.Cleaning Data: At first, the data is cleansed. Users are eliminating unnecessary entries in this area. The data that is noisy can also be eliminated from the dataset.

2.Resizing: resizing the uploaded images with accurate height and width.

3.Edge detecting: canny is one of the edge -detection that uses a multi-stage algorithm to detect a wide range of edges in that image.

4.Contours detection: used for shape- analysis, object detection and recognition

5.Recognition: easy OCR is used to optical character recognition.

C. Machine Learning: This method is implemented with opencv and easyocr's machine learning approach, and the accuracy is evaluated with sklearn.

D. Requirements

pycharm

IV.BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in electricity meter image detection. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

- 1.Import the packages that are necessary.

```
# import the necessary packages
from imutils.perspective import four_point_transform
from imutils import contours
import imutils
import cv2
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from matplotlib import image
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
```

- 2.Upload an image then preprocessing.

```
image = cv2.imread("meter.jpeg")
# pre-process the image by resizing it, converting it to
# grayscale, blurring it, and computing an edge map
image = imutils.resize(image, height=500)
gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
blurred = cv2.GaussianBlur(gray, (5, 5), 0)
edged = cv2.Canny(blurred, 50, 200, 255)
cnts = cv2.findContours(edged.copy(), cv2.RETR_EXTERNAL,
cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)
cnts = imutils.grab_contours(cnts)
cnts = sorted(cnts, key=cv2.contourArea, reverse=True)
displayCnt = None
```

- 3.Then accuracy of an image.

```
from sklearn.datasets import load_digits
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
n_samples = 200
x, y = load_digits(return_sample_indices=False, return_X_y=True, n_samples=n_samples, n_classes_per_class=1)
x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(x, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
logreg = LogisticRegression()
logreg.fit(x_train, y_train)
y_pred = logreg.predict(x_test)
```

- 4.Import easy ocr to text recognition.

```
import easyocr
reader = easyocr.Reader(['en'])
result = reader.readtext(thresh)
text = result[0][-2]
print(text)
cv2.imshow("Output", thresh)
cv2.waitKey(0)
```


5.Then result will be generated.

Fig.2. Input of meter reading

V. RESULT

The result shows that meter reading by extraction of digits on the basis of machine learning openCV and easy OCR. Firstly collecting the data then preprocessing, segmentation, extraction of a digits.

Fig.3.output of meter reading

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a method for reading a meter in online mode. The uploaded image then undergoes preprocessing, segmentation, extraction to get reading of meter as text using machine learning.

In future this concept can be implemented on android applications.

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